

CONCEPT OF PARADIGM.

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Abstract: In this article, the activity paradigm works well in both fundamental and applied psychology. In the latter, it was especially in demand, because it appeared in many ways as a response to the demands of social practice. Like the epistemological paradigm, the activity paradigm has a practical form of expression.

Key words: competent personality formation, psychotherapy, monoideology, ability development, rationality, activity paradigm, objective needs, special techniques.

Аннотация: В данной статье деятельностная парадигма хорошо работает как в фундаментальной, так и в прикладной психологии. В последнем оно было особенно востребовано, поскольку выступало во многом как ответ на требования социальной практики. Как и гносеологическая парадигма, деятельностная парадигма имеет практическую форму выражения.

Ключевые слова: формирование компетентной личности, психотерапия, моноидеология, развитие способностей, рациональность, парадигма деятельности, объективные потребности, специальные методики.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada foliyat paradigmasi ham fundamental, ham amaliy psixologiyada yaxshi ishlaydi. Ikkinchisida u ayniqsa talabga ega bo'ldi, chunki u ko'p jihatdan ijtimoiy amaliyot talablariga javob sifatida paydo bo'ldi. Epistemologik paradigma singari, faoliyat paradigmasi ham amaliy ifoda shakliga ega kabi tushunchalar haqida so`z yuritilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: shaxsni malakali shakllantirish, psixoterapiya, monoideologiyasi, qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish, ratsionallik, faoliyat paradigmasi, ob'ektiv ehtiyojlari, maxsus texnikalar.

PARADIGM (Gr. муѠа) is a scientific way of thinking. A unit of factors that are recognized at the same time and determine a certain scientific research (knowledge). A concept introduced by the positivist G. Berman and widely based for the natural sciences by the American physicist T. Kuhn. In science, it means the unity of beliefs, values, and technical tools adopted in a certain period, and it is ensured that scientific traditions are preserved. A paradigm is a broader concept than a theory, and its change represents a revolution in science. The main paradigms in the explanation of politics: 1) Theological - the divine interpretation of politics and power. 2) Natural - a) politics is defined by the influence of the external natural environment - geographical paradigm; b) politics is defined by the characteristics of living nature - biological paradigm. c) politics is caused by human characteristics - psychological paradigm. 3) Social - politics is interpreted through other spheres of social life. 4) Rational-critical - politics is defined by its factors, for example, conflict - consensus. The activity paradigm works well in both fundamental and applied psychology. In the latter, it was especially in demand, because it appeared in many ways as a response to the demands of social practice. Like the epistemological paradigm, the activity paradigm has a form of practical expression. This form is psychotechnics. Despite the external similarities, technological and psychotechnical paradigms are significantly different from each other. Their main difference is the difference in goals. In the first case, due to the objective needs of the practice, the goal is indifferent to a certain person, and it simply adapts to it with the help of special techniques. Secondly, the goal is the development of a person himself, which gives him the opportunity to cope with increasingly complex educational and production tasks. Human standardization is the result of using a technological paradigm. Developing abilities, finding an individual style of activity is the result of

applying the psychotechnical paradigm. In this sense, one can talk about the internal humanistic direction of the activity paradigm, which brings it closer to the humanistic and existential approaches in psychology in terms of value. The humanistic orientation of the theory appears as one of the criteria of the "eternal value" of the psychological concept within the framework of the post-classical type of rationality announced today (Kornilova, Smirnov, 2016).

Regarding psychotherapy, we believe that the activity paradigm actually rejects any psychotherapy. Recognizing the socio-cultural conditionality of the development of human consciousness and personality (L. S. Vygotsky, S. L. Rubinshtein, A. N. Leontiev, P. Ya. Halperin) prioritize the task of competently forming a conscious culturally developed socially useful person and correcting this formation in psychologically complex situations etc. Raising a full-fledged person is one of the main tasks of society (recall the experience of the Zagorsky orphanage in working with blind children, which was initiated by A. N. Leontiev). With this approach, traditional individual psychotherapy becomes unnecessary as a way of working with a person. It is not surprising that psychotherapy did not exist as a branch of psychology in the USSR (although psychiatry did). The development of psychotherapy began only in the 1990s. and took place against the background of the "collapse" of the monoideology of the activity approach and the penetration of alternative western currents into local psychology.

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